

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15298100

Analysis of Temporal Variations of air Pollutant Concentrations in Sokoto Metropolis, Nigeria

¹Abdullahi Usman Budah, ²Shehu Abdullahi & ³Z.M. Dabo

¹Department of Geography,
Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto, Nigeria

²Department of Integrated Science,
Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto, Nigeria

³Directorate of Academic Planning and Research Development,
Hussaini Adamu Federal Polytechnic, Kazaure, Jigawa, Nigeria
Corresponding author email: usmanabdullah224@gmail.com
Mobile No: 08036043597

ABSTRACT

Air pollution has been identified as a significant environmental challenge often experienced in rapidly developing built-up cities in developing countries. The study analyzed temporal variation of air pollutants (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO₂, SO₂, and CO) in Sokoto Metropolis. Based on land use, ten sampling location were selected for the study. Measurement was carried out on weekly (Monday, Wednesday and Saturday) from 8:00am and 5:00pm in the morning, afternoon and evening for four weeks. PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO₂ and CO concentration exceeded permissible limits of NESREA and WHO. The study showed that there is significant difference between the two seasons (wet and dry) for NO₂, SO₂ and CO with P-value 0.00, 0.00 and 0.004 respectively, there is no significant difference for PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ with P-value 0.264 and 0.913 at 0.05 significant level. Air pollution concentration showed months of dry season with high concentration level, while months of rainy season with low concentration level. Analysis of temporal variability revealed that air pollutants concentrations increased in the morning and evening and on weekdays and decreased during the weekends. The temporal variability of air pollutants in Sokoto Metropolis showed anthropogenic activities were the main sources of air pollution in the area, therefore studies are required to evaluate air pollutant dispersion pattern and to determine the factors influencing air quality in the area.

Keywords: temporal, variation, pollution, metropolis, anthropogenic activities

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution is one of the environmental problems confronting growing cities and is currently the challenge faced by both developed and developing countries (Akinfolarin *et al*, 2018). The World Health Organization (WHO) has ranked air pollution as the 13th major cause of mortality in the world today (WHO, 2015). Several health effects have been associated with short-term (few hours, days, weeks and months) exposure to air pollution (European Environment Agency, 2019; Habeebullah, 2017). Short-term exposure to air pollution can cause damage to the lung function and respiratory infectious diseases such as wheezing, cough and shortness of breath (EEA, 2019; Hosie, 2019). Various anthropogenic activities have either increased the content level of some of the natural pollutants or have added new pollutants to

the air. Consequently, the air quality has deteriorated significantly and the atmosphere in general stands polluted considerably (Sarasamma *et al.*, 2014). Globally, the hazardous impact of air pollution on human health and the environment has been on the rise, particularly in developing countries where most people still generate their own electricity by means of fossil fuel (diesel and petrol) powered electricity generator sets for both commercial and domestic use.

Among the air pollutants of concern are carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, oxides of nitrogen, oxides of sulfur, particulate matter, noise and volatile organic compounds such as benzene, polycyclic hydrocarbons and formaldehyde (WHO, 2018). The effects of the above on human lives are enormous as it causes disease and can result in chronic illness. Apart from the health effects, air pollution contributes to our changing climatic conditions, which are potential sources of threats to local and international communities (Akinfolarin *et al.*, 2018). Exposure to air pollutants has been associated with increased risk of upper respiratory tract diseases such as asthma, inflammation, fibrosis and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, exacerbation of heart disease due to hypertension and degeneration of the cells which line blood vessels, irreparable damage to the central nervous system, as well as cancers. Studies conducted in Ethiopia, Mozambique, and Kenya have established higher prevalence of asthma in urban school children exposed to pollution compared to rural children (WHO, 2018).

The concentration of air pollutants released from various sources in urban areas, vary both in time and in space (Yorkor *et al.*, 2021). Time variations of air pollutants are strongly influenced by changes in human activities and the meteorological conditions of the area (McNeill, 2019). Sokoto urban area is rapidly increasing (Eniolorunda & Dankani, 2012). Increasing population and motor vehicle number and use, expanding commercial and industrial activities, with the attendant waste generation, are the major sources of air pollution in the study area. Temporal variation of air pollution of the study area have not been assessed. Understanding temporal changes in air quality and an assessment of air quality indices of an area are important in evaluating effects of air pollution on human health. To this end, this study analyzed temporal variation of air pollutants during the dry and wet season in Sokoto metropolis. This is necessary for future health impact assessment and the development of air quality management plans and for the protection of public health. Thus, the result of this study can be used by policy makers to decide on locations to install air pollution monitoring stations in the area.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

Sokoto Metropolis is located between latitudes 13°01' 10" 11"N to 13°05' 10" 11"N and longitudes 5°01' 31" 11"E to 5°01' 71" 11"E. It covers 16km radius from Shehu Kangiwa Square and is bounded by Kware Local Government to the North, Wamakko to the West, and Bodinga to the south, situated in the Sudan savanna (Olayinka, 2003). Sokoto Metropolis constitutes the whole of Sokoto North and Sokoto South Local Government Areas and parts of Dange/Shuni and Wamakko local government areas respectively. The area experiences two distinct seasons: the dry season (October–April) and wet season (May–September) (SOSG, 2011).

Fig 1: The study area

Data Collection: For this study, ten (10) sampling points were purposively selected among the most notorious flash points owned to the fact that they are typically characterized by industrial, artisanal and heavily commercial activities which emits gaseous pollutants and particulates, also taking into consideration the human exposure to this pollutants gases in the Metropolitan area. These sample sites were the Federal Government College roundabout Sokoto, Giginya Barrack, Unguwar Rogo, Kofar Taramniya, Illela Garage, Tsohuwar Kasuwa (Old Market), Dandima Roundabout, Cenral Bank Bridge, Arkilla Housing and Gidan man Ada Roundabout. The sampling was carried out in two months between the periods of dry and wet season in the month of March 2020 and September 2021, in three different periods of the day (morning, afternoon and evening).

Automatic methods was use in measurement. These methods produce high resolution measurements at a single point for pollutants such as O_3 , NO_x , SO_2 , CO and PM_{10} or $PM_{2.5}$ (Harrop, 2018). Pollutant were measured using Bosen Portable multi gas detector for the NO_2 , SO_2 , CO and particulate matter ($PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10}). These are hand-held instruments that detect and measure the concentrations of gasses and particulate matter in part per million (ppm) and micrograms per cubic meter ($\mu g/m^3$). The BH-4S 19038504 model that has external digital temperature and humidity sensors was used; this gave accurate measurements of gasses and particulate matter devoid of the influence and interference of relative humidity (M and A Instruments Inc. 2018). The hand-held GPS (Global Positioning System Garmin GPS map 78s receiver) was used to obtain the coordinates of the selected locations.

Data analysis: Descriptive and inferential statistical methods were employed to analyse the pollutants ($PM_{2.5}$, PM_{10} , NO_2 , SO_2 and CO) data obtain from the sample sites. Descriptive statistics, specifically the mean and standard deviation, were calculated to summarize the data. The concentration level of were shown on table. Analysis of variance was used to determine significant differences existed in the data across seasons and temporal intervals. While temporal variability was determine by analysing difference across specific time points.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The statistical summary of measured pollutants concentration in the study area is shown in Table 1. The parameters, range, mean and standard deviation in comparison with the National Environmental Standards Enforcement Agency (NESREA) and World Health Organisation (WHO) are shown in Table 1. The result (Table 1) shows that the mean value of PM_{2.5} 48.6µm/m³ exceeded NESREA and WHO permissible limit; mean value of PM₁₀ 52.96µm/m³ exceeded NESREA and WHO permissible limit; while the mean value of NO₂ 0.12ppm is within the NESREA standards limit, but exceeded WHO permissible limit; the mean value of SO₂ 0.01ppm is below NESREA and WHO permissible limit; the mean concentration of CO 10.80ppm exceeded NESREA and WHO permissible limit. These result show that the area is polluted by PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO₂ and CO. The concentration level of air pollutants observed in the study area can caused adverse health hazards to the public (Hosie, 2019).

Table 1: Statistical Summary of Pollutants Measured in the Study Area

Parameters	Range	Mean±SD	Standards	
			NESREA	WHO
PM _{2.5} (µg/m ³)	13.00-181.00	48.6±30.78	25µm/m ³	25µm/m ³
PM ₁₀ (µg/m ³)	12.00-210.60	52.96±36.22	150µm/m ³	50µm/m ³
NO ₂ (ppm)	0.00-0.80	0.12±0.18	0.12ppm	0.04ppm
SO ₂ (ppm)	0.00-0.10	0.01±0.03	0.12ppm	0.02ppm
CO (ppm)	0.00-81.00	10.80±12.19	0.05ppm	9ppm

The mean seasonal variations of pollutants in the study is shown on Table 2. The test of variance was at 0.05 level of significance between the pollutants concentrations in wet and dry season. The statistics shows there exists a significant difference between the seasons (wet and dry) for NO₂, SO₂ and CO. This is because the calculated P-value of 0.00, 0.00 and 0.004 were found to be lower than 0.05 level of significance (Thomas, 2014). However, there is no significant difference in the reading of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ because the calculated P value of 0.264 and 0.913 was found to be greater than the 0.05 level of significance (Zalakeviciute *et al.*, 2020).

Table 2: Mean Seasonal Variations of Gaseous and Particulate Matter Pollutants

Parameters	Seasons		P-value	Mean value
	Wet	Dry		
PM _{2.5} (µg/m ³)	51.17±36.22	46.03±24.09	0.264	48.6±30.78
PM ₁₀ (µg/m ³)	52.67±38.34	53.26±34.19	0.913	52.96±36.22
NO ₂ (ppm)	0.00±0.00	0.24±0.19	0.000	0.12±0.18
SO ₂ (ppm)	0.00±0.01	0.02±0.04	0.000	0.01±0.03
CO (ppm)	13.39±12.45	8.21±11.4	0.004	10.80±12.19

Table 3: Analysis of variance for temporal air quality data in dry season

Time	NO ₂	SO ₂	CO	PM _{2.5}	PM ₁₀
Morning	0.313a	0.006b	4.77b	50.376a	58.780ab
Afternoon	0.128b	0.035a	5.420b	31.090b	39.196b
Evening	0.279a	0.019ab	14.446a	56.620b	61.8000a

The analysis of variance for temporal air quality in dry season in the study area is shown in Table 3. The emission concentration levels of NO₂ were 0.313ppm, 0.128ppm and 0.279ppm for morning, afternoon and evening respectively ((Table 3). The result show high concentration in the morning and evening,

which is attributed to early morning rush to school of pupils and students, incoming of workers/business operators from peri-urban area of Metropolis and cooking of morning meals by the households, there is also movement of trucks/trailers from cement company carrying loads of cement which can also exacerbate emission of NO₂ at FGC roundabout and Giginya Barracks which is mostly residential and open space in the study area. The emission concentration in the evening is attributed to high traffic congestion as worker, marketers and business operators have all closed and the need to go home causes gridlocks of traffic and also cooking by households for evening meals (Okunola *et al* 2012).

SO₂ emission level were 0.006ppm, 0.035ppm and 0.019ppm in the morning, afternoon and evening respectively (Table 3). The evening emission concentration level was low and shows no variation at the sampling points. The concentration level was only high 0.035ppm in the afternoon at Dandima roundabout, Arkilla housing and Gidan man Ada sites which is a light and heavy industrial area of the study and is attributed to incomplete combustion of fuel containing sulphur oxides coming mostly from the vehicular traffic and industries from the area (Khodier *et al.*, 2012) and also due to high temperature in the dry season month of march (Oji & Adamu, 2020).

CO emission level in the evening was high 14.446ppm at Giginya Barracks and FGC roundabout, this is associated to the high vehicular and traffic congestion of heavy duty trucks at the road intersection within the study area. The evening time is the period most marketers/business operators closed and the cooking of evening meals by the households (Thomas, 2014). The CO concentration was low in the morning and afternoon due to less activities (Oji & Adamu, 2020).

The emission concentration level of PM_{2.5} were high in the evening 56.620ppm, followed by morning 50.376ppm and afternoon 31.090ppm, this indicate high activities in the evening and morning which is attributed to vehicular emission from mostly diesel engine trucks/trailers, the activities of cement company and open burning in the study area and also the industrial activity is the major land used in the area (Dandima and Arkilla housing). The emission level of PM₁₀ was high in the evening and morning 61.800ppm and 58.780ppm, and the PM₁₀ emission levels in the morning shows no variation at the sampling points. The emission concentration is associated with re-suspension of coarse particles. The re-suspension coarse particles come mainly from street dust and road surfaces and also wearing of tyres due to high activities in these periods of the day and also the presence of industries, ware houses market and blacksmithing activities at the site (Khodier *et al.*, 2012).

The Analysis of variance for temporal air quality data in wet season is shown in Table 4. The wet season emission concentration level of SO₂ in the study was low in the afternoon 0.003ppm, morning and evening has 0.000ppm (Table 4). The low emission level is attributed to meteorological influence of rainfall which has a dilution effect on pollutants concentration (Oji & Adamu, 2020). CO emission concentration level were high throughout the day, with evening having the highest emission level of 17.150ppm, followed by afternoon 13.253ppm and morning 9.903ppm all at Giginya Barracks and FGC roundabout which are intersection of two major highways in the study area. This result to high vehicular and traffic congestion due to the need by workers, marketers and business operators to closed and go home, the open burning at the sites and also burning of tyres and the use of power generators at the sites (residential) due erratic power supply (Okunola *et al.*, 2012).

The emission concentration level of PM_{2.5} is high in evening 78.060ppm, followed by 44.200ppm in morning and 31.253ppm in afternoon (Table 4). This is as a result of grid lock of traffic, open burning and demolition/construction activities at the site and re-suspension of particles dust by motorist at Dandima roundabout (Aliyu & Botai, 2018). PM₁₀ emission level was also high 80.773ppm in the evening followed by 44.576ppm in morning and 32.646ppm in afternoon. This is attributed to the demolition and construction activities at the site, couple with heavy traffic of diesel engines of lorries/trailers/trucks and buses which fly the route and the intersection of road that connects two major highways, the area is also commercial/light industrial (Olayinka *et al.*, 2015).

Table 4: Analysis of variance for temporal air quality data in wet season

Time	SO ₂	CO	PM _{2.5}	PM ₁₀
Morning	0.000b	9.903b	44.200b	44.576b
Afternoon	0.003b	13.130b	31.253b	32.647b
Evening	0.000b	17.150b	78.060a	80.773a

CONCLUSION

The study found high level of air pollution in old market area of the Metropolis, which poses hazards to public health. This study provided the knowledge of temporal variability of air pollutants in the Metropolis. Air pollutants concentration were found to be higher in the months of dry season and lower in the month of rainy season. The temporal variability of air pollutants concentrations showed a pronounced difference in the periods of the day (morning, afternoon and evening). Generally, concentrations of air pollutants showed increase during the morning and evening periods of the day when human activities are high. It is concluded that anthropogenic activities are the major source of air pollution in the area. Therefore, further studies are required to evaluate the factors influencing air pollution in the area and to determine air pollutant dispersion pattern base on the meteorological condition of the area.

REFERENCES

- Aliyu, Y. A. and Botai, J. O (2018) Reviewing the local and global implications of air pollution trends in Zaria, northern Nigeria. *Journal of urban climate* Retrieved 5 december 2019 from: www.elsevier.com/locate/ucim <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ucim.2018.08.008>
- Anjaneyulu, Y. (2005). *Introduction to Environmental Science, India*: BS Publications Hyderabad.
- Ayodele, J. T. and Bayero, A. S. (2010). Lead and Zinc Concentrations in Hair and Nail of some Kano Inhabitants. *African Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, Vol. 3(3): 164-170
- Akinfolarin, O. M. Obunwo, C. C. and Boisa, N. (2018). Air quality characteristics of emerging industrial areas in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *European Journal of Scientific Research*. Pp 43(1), 7-14.
- EEA. (2019). Air quality in Europe — 2019 report (No 10/2019). Retrieved from European Environment Agency, Luxembourg. <http://europa.eu>.
- Environmental Protection Agency (2014). Air Quality Index a Guide to Air Quality and Your Health. www.epa.org Retrieved 11December 2019
- Eniolorunda, N. B, and Dankani, I. M. (2012) Assessment Of Urban Growth Pattern In Sokoto Metroplis, Nigeria Using Multitemporal Sateelite Data. *Nigeria Geographical Journal, Volume 8(1) June 2012: 1358-4319*
- Garba, M. D. and Yunusa, M. S. (2016) Assessing gaseous pollutants and air quality in some areas of Kano metropolis, Kano, Nigeria. International Conference on Environmental and Economic Impact on Sustainable Development. www.witconferences.com doi: 102495/EID160121.
- Habeebullah, T. M., Munir, S., Morsy, E. A., & Mohammed, A. M. F. (2014). Spatial and Temporal Analysis of Air Pollution in Makkah, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. 5th International Conference on Environmental Science and Technology. IPCBEE, IACSIT Press, Singapore, 69(14); 65-70. DOI: 10.7763/IPCBEE.
- Harrop, O. (2018) Air quality assessment and management. A practical guide. CRC Press.
- Hosie, P. (2019). Air Pollution: The Hidden Killer in Our Midst. Health Effects Institute (HEI). Retrieved from www.investigativejournal.com/reports on 6th September, 2021.
- Ibrahim, A. A. Ali, B. (2022) Assessment of Population Growth on Housing Demand in Sokoto Metropolis. *International journal of research publication and reviews*, vol. 3, pp.2042-2050.
- Krzyzanowski, M. and Gapp, C. (2011). Exposure to air pollution (particulate matter) in outdoor air. WHO European Centre for Environment and Health, Bonn, Germany. Retrieved 14 January 2020 from www.euro.who.int/ENHIS.

- Khodier, M. Sharmy, M. Alghamdi, M. Zhong, M. Sun, H. Chen, L.C. Costa, M. and Maclejezc, P.M. (2012) Source Apportionment and Elemental Composition of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ in Jeddah city, Saudi Arabia. *Atmospheric pollution research*, 3. Pp.331-340
- McNeill, V.F. (2019) Addressing the Global Air Pollution Crisis: Chemistry's Role. *Trends Chemistry*, 1(1): 1-8.
- Ndoke, P.N., Akpan, U.G. and Kato, M.E. (2010). Contributions of Vehicular Traffic to Carbon Dioxide Emissions in Kaduna and Abuja, Northern Nigeria. *Leonardo Electronic Journal of Practices and Technologies*. Pp. 81-90
- NESREA (2014) National Environmental (Air Quality Control) Regulations 2014. Lagos, Nigeria. Federal Government Printers.
- Okunola, O. J. Uzairu, A. Gimba C. E. and Ndukwe, G. I. (2012). Assessment of Gaseous Pollutants along High Traffic Roads in Kano, Nigeria. *International Journal of Environment and Sustainability*, Vol. 1 No. 1, pp. 1-15
- Osimobi, O. J. Yorkor, B. and Nwankwo, C. A. (2019). Evaluation of daily pollutant standard index and air quality index in a university campus in Nigeria using PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} particulate matter. *Journal of Science, Technology and Environment Informatics*, 07(02), 517-532.
- Olayinka, O.O. Adedeji, O.H. and Ajibola, F.O. (2015) Monitoring Gaseous and Particulate Air Pollutants near Major Highways in Abeokuta, Nigeria. *Journal of Science and Environmental Management*. Vol. 19 (4) www.ajol.info and www.bioline.org.br/ja Retrieved 4 December 2019
- Olayinka, Y. B. (2003) *Senior Secondary Atlas, 2nd Edition*. Longman, Nigeria Plc. Oba Akra Ikeja Lagos
- Oji, S. and Adamu, H. (2020) Correlation between air pollutants concentration and meteorological factors on seasonal air quality variation. *Journal of Air Pollution and Health*. <http://japh.tums.ac.ir>. Retrieved 24 July 2021.
- Sarasamma, J.D. and Narayanan, B. K. (2014). Air quality assessment in the surrounding of KMML Industrial Area, Chavara in Kerala, South India. *Aerosol and Air Quality Res*. 14:179-1778.
- Sokoto State Government (2011). *Tourist Attractions in Sokoto State*. Published by Sokoto State Government Nigeria.
- Thomas, N. (2014). *An assessment of air pollution in Minna town, Niger state, Nigeria*. (Unpublished Masters dissertation) Ahnadu Bello University Zaria, Nigeria.
- Tsafe, A. I. Abdulrahman, F. W. Zuru, A. A. and Ayodele, J. T. (2010) Atmospheric Level of SO₂ in Sokoto Metropolis, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Basic and Applied Science*, 18(1):101-105
- WHO. (2015) World Health Organization Air quality guidelines for Particulate matter ozone, nitrogen dioxide and sulphur dioxide. Global Update 2006 Summary of Risk Assessment.
- WHO. (2018). Health effects of particulate matter: Policy implications for countries in Eastern Europe, Caucasus and central Asia. WHO Regional Office for Europe, UN City, Marmorvej 51, DK2100 Copenhagen Ø, Denmark. Retrieved 4 December 2019 from <http://www.euro.who.int/pubrequest>
- Yorkor, B., Leton, T. G., and Ugbebor, J. N. (2021). Characterization and Identification of Air Pollutants Sources in Ogoni area, Niger Delta, Nigeria. *Uniport Journal of Engineering and Scientific Research*, 6(1): 50-58.
- Zalakeviciute, R. Alexandrino, K. Rybarczyk, Y. Debut, A. Vizuete, K. and Diaz, M. (2020) Seasonal variations in PM₁₀ inorganic composition in the Andean city. *Journal of nature research* 10:17049 Retrieved 15 August 2021 from <https://www.nature.com/scientificreports/doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-72541-2>.